

POLICY PAPER

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**CYBER DIPLOMACY AND SOCIAL MEDIA: A
PARADOX FOR PEACE BUILDING**

AUTHOR: Danielle Jacon Ayres Pinto

POLICY STATEMENT

Despite its enormous conflicts, the contemporary world has proved to be the most peaceful period in the world since the two great world wars. Never before have States exchanged their offensive and violent capacities through interaction that promote conversation between them, trade, and especially, create rules to improve and facilitate their relations in the international system. Traditional diplomacy has become a central element in States' political action. However, with the emergence of new information and communication technologies and the new dynamics of virtual sociability through social media, this diplomacy has come under enormous pressure (01). The negotiations within a traditional diplomatic board began to occupy the public space of social media apps where political leaders started to interact and make political movements (02). Thus, the virtual space that for many was seen exclusively as a new domain of war has become, through its political use, a possible new tool for peace-building and promoter of great negotiations between States.

BACKGROUND

The virtual space, also known as cyberspace, despite not being a novelty for its varied users, still implies a sociability domain that generates constant doubts and misinterpretations about its true dimension. One of the most constant mistakes is its direct association with the internet as if both were the same (03). The internet is part of the so-called cyberspace; however, the large volume of digital traffic moved by it makes it the main dimension of human sociability today and therefore transforms information and communication technologies into an effective power element (04).

According to data from the website Statista.com (05), at the end of 2020, there were 4.66 billion active users on the internet, of those 4.14 billion are active users of social media and 4.08 billion access their social media exclusively via cell phone, that is, 59% of the world population uses the Internet nowadays, and 91% of this use is made via cell phone.

Thus, the internet also materializes through social media, applications that aim to increase social interaction in between people, breaking down communication barriers and creating new possibilities for dialogue. The interaction, previously impossible, between an ordinary citizen with its politicians or even with the State's senior officials today can be common and continuous within social media (06)

This new communicational dynamic changes the reality of power in the international sphere - we will see a process of transition and diffusion of power (04), where actors with less capacity for direct influence in the international system will use these digital tools to build their influence. On the other hand, we will have new non-state actors with the capacity to promote global consequences, in a clear movement to spread a power that before was only possible to be carried out by the State.

FINDINGS

Faced with this growing dynamic of the entry of new technologies in human sociability, we started to see, in 2007, the existence of politicians around the world creating Twitter and Facebook accounts. Barack Obama was the pioneer in this movement. In 2007, when he was a pre-candidate for the USA's presidency by the Democratic party, he started to interact in social media and be followed by thousands of people. Obama's behavior has spread to world leaders, who have come to create a new way of doing politics outside traditional standards. Thus, in 2020, 189 countries on the globe already had their official Twitter accounts and added to them the accounts of their maximum leaders in the vast majority of times.

For the expert and professor at the University of Copenhagen Rebecca Adler-Nissen (07), although this phenomenon can promote a new way of improving diplomatic negotiation processes and, consequently, the peace agreements that high-ranking members of countries normally promote interstate organizations, it also poses a threat. For, normally, state leaders' use of social media destroyed the three central pillars of the diplomatic process: time, space, and tactics and protocols.

Many leaders began to use their social media to interfere in diplomatic processes at the exact moments when such negotiations took place, putting pressure from society and the press within the negotiation process, all without having such a tactic previously agreed with their diplomatic corps.

On other occasions, leaders responded directly to their counterparts in the face of false news that had come to their attention, as was the case in 2016 of the Pakistani Prime Minister's answer to the Israeli government on a question of a nuclear attack threat he would have done. The threat was actually Fake News that had been falsely disseminated by groups opposed to the government. Without following legitimate diplomatic means of responding to such a situation, it made the Pakistani Prime Minister exalt himself in retaliation against Israel on his own Twitter.

To worsen these attitudes' dimension, great leaders started to have their accounts followed by thousands of people, often being these digital media spaces, the only source of information for these individuals. An example of this was the account of former US President Donald Trump, who in 2020 was followed by more than 81 million people on Twitter (08) and who, during the period of power transition between him and Joe Biden, was even blocked in this media for spreading fake news and hate speech.

CONCLUSIONS

This kind of use of social media by world leaders as tools for exercising individual politics proves to be, in the short term, something quite reckless. The cyberspace that should be the space to effectively promote peaceful means of dialogue, with its inadequate use to reinforce political pressures and quick responses among countries, causes serious damage to traditional diplomacy and temporarily makes the use of social media impossible to the consolidation of effective digital diplomacy that can give citizens the ability to also interact in this process in an organized, rational and effective way. Thus, as used by political leaders today, cyberspace seems to reinforce the rhetoric of the traditional conflict among states.

SUGGESTIONS

Briefly, we now suggest some measures that could change this scenario:

- 1) Creation of rules and limits (national and international) for the use of social media by State actors, their leaders, and their official representatives;
- 2) Enhance the traditional role of the diplomatic corps and improve the means for them to use new technologies, especially social media, to promote more agreements and participation by society in its peace-building processes;
- 3) Increase the knowledge and digital training of the population, so they can understand the new digital dynamics and know how to charge their leaders for appropriate behavior in this sphere;
- 4) Think of national and international ways to punish the official spread of Fake News by world leaders in their official social media accounts.

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